

Martin et al.: REPRODUCTIVE TRACT SIZE AND POSITION

Supplementary Table S1. Posterior mean, posterior standard deviation (PSD) and highest posterior density (HPD) interval of the genetic parameters resulting from the threshold animal model (liability scale) for the reproductive size and position score, estimated on records from 490 Holstein cows over three years in one herd.

	Mean	PSD	low HPD	high HPD
σ_p^2	0.261	0.005	0.253	0.268
σ_a^2	0.040	0.005	0.032	0.047
σ_e^2	0.175	0.004	0.169	0.183
$\sigma_{pe_w}^2$	0.037	0.004	0.031	0.044
$\sigma_{pe_a}^2$	0.008	0.003	0.004	0.012
h^2	0.153	0.017	0.123	0.178
r_w	0.328	0.015	0.306	0.354
r_a	0.185	0.018	0.156	0.213

σ_p^2 : phenotypic variance; σ_a^2 : additive genetic variance; σ_e^2 : residual variance; $\sigma_{pe_w}^2$: within-lactation permanent environmental variance; $\sigma_{pe_a}^2$: across-lactation permanent environmental variance; h^2 : heritability; r_w : within-lactation repeatability; r_a : across-lactations repeatability